

EXPLORING THE MARE-HIGHLAND TRANSITION IN THE MONTES HAEMUS-SERENITATIS-TRANQUILLITATIS REGION. A. Ariza-Pardo (adriana.arizapardo@phd.unich.it)^{1,2}, L. Marinangeli¹, C. van der Bogert², M. Pondrelli¹, H. Hiesinger², W. Iqbal² and L. Wueller². ¹Università G. d'Annunzio Chieti-Pescara, Italy, ²Institut für Planetologie, University of Münster, Germany.

Introduction: The Serenitatis basin and surrounding regions have been investigated since the earliest lunar geological mapping efforts, including the geologic map of the Mare Serenitatis region [1], the geologic map of the nearside of the Moon [2], and broader syntheses of lunar stratigraphy and geologic history [3]. Subsequent studies have further examined the volcanic stratigraphy and ages of mare basalts within Mare Serenitatis and Mare Tranquillitatis using crater size-frequency distribution analyses and regional stratigraphic relationships [4].

Previous high-resolution geological mapping efforts at Apollo landing sites have demonstrated the importance of integrated morphologic and stratigraphic analyses for refining lunar surface evolution models and regional stratigraphy [5-7].

The southeastern Serenitatis–Tranquillitatis–Montes Haemus region represents a particularly compelling target for geological mapping and exploration because it combines mare basalt plains, massif-forming highland materials associated with basin-ring uplift, tectonic structures, impact-exposed stratigraphic contacts, and compositionally heterogeneous regolith within a compact basin-margin setting. In addition, the region includes several volcanic dark mantle deposits, such as the Sulpicius Gallus pyroclastics, along the northwestern margin of Mare Serenitatis, which has been interpreted as the product of explosive volcanic activity [8,9]. Such deposits have attracted interest for their potential use for in situ resource utilization (ISRU), because of their fine-grained volcanic materials and possible enrichment in water-, iron- and titanium-bearing phases [10].

Figure 1. Regional context of the study area. Base image from the LROC WAC global mosaic [11].

This study presents a geological synthesis of the area bounded by 9°E-30°E and 9°N-24°N, covering approximately 283,000 km², with the aim of improving the regional geological framework of this mare-highlands transition zone and supporting future lunar exploration and resource assessment studies (Figure 1).

Data and Methods: Geological mapping is being conducted in ArcGIS Pro through the integration of multiple orbital datasets, including LROC Wide Angle Camera (WAC) imagery [11], Kaguya Terrain Camera (TC) mosaics and digital terrain models [12], SLDEM2015 topography [13], and Clementine multispectral data [14]. These datasets provide complementary information on surface morphology, topography, spectral properties, and regional context at multiple spatial scales.

Geological units are delineated through the combined interpretation of albedo variations observed in WAC imagery (morning and evening mosaics), morphologic characteristics, topographic relationships, and spectral properties derived from Clementine data, which enable the identification of mare basalt units, highland materials, and mare-highland transitional contacts. Derived products such as slope maps and hillshade visualizations are used to support the identification of structural trends, surface roughness variations, and unit boundaries.

This approach follows established methodologies for planetary geological mapping based on the integration of morphologic and topographic datasets within a GIS framework [15].

Results: Preliminary analysis of the study area indicates the presence of three main geological domains. Mare basalts associated with southern Mare Serenitatis occupy approximately 42% of the study area, while mare basalts belonging to northeastern Mare Tranquillitatis account for roughly 27%. The remaining ~31% corresponds to highland materials related to the Montes Haemus massif, representing uplifted crustal blocks associated with the Serenitatis basin ring structure.

The spatial relationships between these geological units reveal a complex mare-highlands transition zone characterized by embayment contacts, structural deformation, and superposed impact features. In several locations, mare basalts embay the margins of the Montes Haemus highlands, suggesting multiple episodes of volcanic resurfacing following the formation of the Serenitatis basin.

The region preserves evidence of basin-ring uplift expressed in the Montes Haemus highlands [1,3], together with mare embayment relationships along

basin margins and localized pyroclastic mantling deposits [3,8,9]. Tectonic deformation within the mare plains is expressed by wrinkle ridges and rille systems, which likely reflect compressional and extensional stresses associated with volcanic loading and lithospheric adjustment [3,16]. In addition, several impact craters expose stratigraphic contacts between mare and highland materials, including Mene-laus, Al-Bakri, and Plinius, providing important markers for reconstructing the regional geological evolution of the Serenitatis-Tranquillitatis transition zone [3,5-7].

Topographic analysis indicates that approximately 94% of the mapped terrain exhibits slopes below 7°, consistent with the dominance of gently sloping basaltic plains. Steeper slopes are primarily concentrated in massif sectors, crater rims, and structurally disrupted margins. Spectral observations further suggest compositional heterogeneity across the region, including sectors enriched in mafic materials and localized terrains containing pyroclastic or regolith-rich deposits.

Discussion: The integration of topographic, morphologic, and spectral datasets enables improved identification of mare-highland contacts and supports the interpretation of stratigraphic relationships across the Serenitatis-Tranquillitatis-Montes Haemus transition zone. Integrated geological mapping approaches have proven essential for interpreting Apollo landing-site geology and refining lunar stratigraphic frameworks [5-7].

The regional framework developed in this study will provide a basis for future crater size-frequency distribution analyses, which can contribute to improved constraints on regional lunar chronology models [17]. Individual mare basalt flows on the lunar nearside typically range from approximately 20 to 220 m in thickness, with average values of 30-60 m, reflecting multiple volcanic resurfacing episodes within mare basins [18].

The geological diversity of the Serenitatis-Tranquillitatis transition zone also highlights its potential relevance for future exploration and resource assessment in non-polar lunar environments, particularly in the context of science-driven site characterization and potential ISRU studies [10]. The Sulpicius Gallus pyroclastic deposit, interpreted as a product of explosive volcanic activity along the Serenitatis basin margin, is one region for investigating of lunar volcanic processes and evaluating potential resource-rich terrains [8,9].

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